

Communicating Learning Instruction through Dance: Teachers' Perceptions of the Potential of Dance as a Teaching Approach

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Abstract

Background of Study: Dance as a learning style has the potential to be an innovative and effective learning method for improving the quality of learning, particularly for elementary school students.

Objective: This research aims to understand teacher perceptions of dance's potential as a teaching and learning strategy.

Methodology: A survey method was employed using an interview observation sheet as the instrument. The research involved 26 elementary school teachers in Semarang.

Result: Based on the interview results, it was found that many teachers have not developed the learning approaches by communicating dance as a learning style in the learning process. The interview results show that 69.2% of teachers have not implemented dance as a learning style, 23.1% have implemented it, and 7.7% have implemented it infrequently. Regarding

teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a learning style, the interview results reveal that 86% of teachers believe that dance can have an impact on students so they can know it well (knowing the good things), 81% of teachers state that dance as a learning style influences students' interest and desire in learning (desiring the good things), 85% of teachers perceive that dance as an instructional approach makes the students easier to imitate well (examplifying the good things), 85% of teachers respond that it can have an impact that students are easy to love properly (loving the good things), 89% of teachers believe that dance as a learning style significantly impact on the students' good practices (acting the good things).

Unique Contribution: This research highlights teachers' perceptions of dance's potential as a current learning style and its potential to be developed as a more effective and innovative learning instruction.

Conclusion: Teachers' perceptions of dance's potential as a teaching style are positive, but the current level of implementation is poor.

Key Recommendation: Teachers should develop a comprehensive learning strategy to enhance the quality of learning through dance as a learning style.

Keywords: teacher perceptions, dance, learning style

Introduction

This research is about teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a learning style. Dance as a learning style can enhance students' social-emotional competencies because dance provides opportunities for self-awareness, nonverbal expression, and synchronisation (Kotaman et al., 2024). It is not only a form of cultural expression but also can be a tool in communicating learning instruction more effectively, particularly in enhancing students' understanding and participation (Scholarworksacwu & Duvall, 2018). Moreover, through dance learning, the teachers can convey the main learning messages, especially those related to character-based learning for the students (Wijayanti & Andriani, 2020). Creative and innovative dance learning positively impacts the students' personal development and provides a meaningful learning experience (Sitti Rahmah et al., 2023). As a learning style, dance can integrate with other subjects because it is a generalizable learning method (Donald, 1991).

In the context of learning, the teachers' instructions play an important role in ensuring that students can understand and master the lesson (Almoslamani, 2022). However, not all teachers have the same understanding of how to communicate the learning instructions effectively. Some teachers may see the dance as an innovative and beneficial learning method in enhancing students' kinesthetic skills, while others may feel a lack of confidence in using dance as a teaching tool. Many teachers have not communicated dance as a learning style so that it results in learning method. So far, the teachers still rarely use dance method as learning instruction tool, especially in delivering character-based messages for students (Prasetiyo, 2024). So far, the teachers still rarely communicate dance as a way of learning methods to convey learning, especially in character education (Ika, et al., 2024).

The specific issue which is researched in this study is the teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a learning style which can be communicated as a learning instruction. Therefore, the teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a teaching style become an important

aspect to be explored, to determine how far this method can be adopted in learning (Anggraeni et al., 2024). Teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a learning style need to be elaborated more specifically to produce the students' good learning qualities, which impact their learning outcomes and character development (Payne & Costas, 2021). The critical aspects related to the potential of dance as a learning style have not been widely communicated by teachers as instructions in learning (Supeni & Harini, 2021). Many teachers have not communicated dance as one of the learning instructions. Focusing on the potential of dance as a learning style, this condition needs to be more deeply communicated because dance as a learning style can positively impact the students' character education (Cuellar-Moreno & Caballero-Juliá, 2019). By emphasising dance as a learning style, this study aims to bridge the discrepancy between the teachers' perceptions of the current potential of dance as a learning style and the potential of dance as a learning style that can be empowered as a good and more innovative learning instruction and have an impact on the students' characters.

In recent years, have researched that dance education help to realize the students' potential for self – development, self – confidence, problem solving, and creativity, this reinforces the idea that the potential of dance as a learning style provides an important role which needs to be communicated by the teachers as instruction in learning. The research also shows that dance provides a physical and sensory contextual response which are essential for holistically understanding the learning material(Brown-Aliffi, 2022). The active involvement of students in a physical and concrete learning experience through dancing allows the students to learn through bodily experience, and reflections on this experience can transform an abstract concept into reality, creating enjoyable learning. The potential of dance as a current learning style needs to be developed to provide more differentiated student learning styles that provide a more meaningful student learning experience.

However, there are still challenges in implementing dance as a part of teaching strategies. The lack of training for the teachers, limited facilities, and cultural barriers or the perceptions that dance is only relevant with the arts. Those are some of the factors that may hinder the use of this method (An et al., 2019). Therefore, it is important to understand how the teachers perceive and assess the potential of dance in learning, as well as the obstacles which they face in implementing it. So that there is a need for continuous research and development which are more applicable in the application of dance as a learning instruction and making the dance as learning style for the students (Payne & Costas, 2021) . With some issues which have been described, this study aims to explore teachers' perceptions regarding the potential of dance as a teaching style in elementary school students. The result of this research is expected to provide insight into the benefits and challenges of using dance in learning and provide recommendations in developing more effective teaching strategies.

Research Purpose

This research aims to determine teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a teaching style. This research aims to address the lack of communication that dance can be empowered as a learning instruction to create creative and innovative learning, creating active students' involvements in physical and concrete learning experience in dance, the students will receive

the opportunity of learning through bodily experience, reflecting on this experience can transform abstract concepts into realities thus creating enjoyable learning. The main research questions guiding of this study include: how do the teachers communicate dance as a learning style? How do the teachers' perceptions of the dance as a learning style? What challenges do the teachers face in communicating of dance as a learning instruction? By focusing on these questions, this research seeks to provide actionable insights and practical solutions to improve the communication of dance as a learning instruction and the potential of dance as a learning style. Emphasising the potential of dance as a learning style is crucial because this strategy can be empowered as a learning instruction to create creative and innovative learning, creating active student engagement in the learning experience.

Methods

Research Design

This research used a survey method to determine teachers' perceptions about the potential of dance as a learning style (Cresswell et al., 2003). A descriptive qualitative research design aims to describe the state or characteristics of the phenomenon observed based on numerical and statistical analysis.

Research Population and Sample

This research's population consisted of 26 elementary school teachers in Semarang. The sample selection was conducted by considering an adequate representation of the entire population.

Sampling Technique

The sampling technique used was purposive sampling (Cresswell et al., 2003). Purposive sampling technique was chosen because this research required the samples which had direct experience in art education in elementary school. Inclusion criteria included the teachers who had taught art education in elementary school. Purposive sampling technique ensured that the selected sample was relevant to the research objectives and could prove information deeply. (Cresswell et al., 2003).

Data Collection Instruments

The data collection instrument which is used in this research includes observation sheets and questionnaires. Observation sheets are used to analyze the teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a learning style (Cresswell et al., 2003). Questionnaires consist of series closed questions on a Likert scale by Abdullah (2015). The data, which were collected from observation sheets and questionnaire copies, were analysed by using descriptive statistics.

Validity and Reliability of Instruments

The instrument of validity was tested through content validity by involving the experts of the field of education to assess the suitability of the items with concepts which were measured (Cresswell et al., 2003). The construction validity test was conducted by using confirmatory factor analysis.

Result

Teachers' Interview Results on the Application of Dance as a Teaching Style

Based on the interview results, it was found that many teachers had not developed learning by communicating dance as a learning style. This was reinforced by the observations made on 26 elementary school dance teachers in Semarang, who responded that 26 of the 26 elementary school teachers answered that they had not implemented learning by communicating dance as a learning style. The observation results can be seen through the following diagram

Diagram 1: The results of the teachers' responses

From diagram 1 above, it can be explained that out of 26 elementary school teachers in Semarang city who were interviewed, 69.2 % of the teachers answered that they had not implemented dance learning as a learning style. This is due to several factors, such as limited school facilities, limited teachers' competencies and students' conditions. School facilities which become a problem are those schools which do not have learning facilities and infrastructures which support the teachers in implementing dance as a learning style in the classroom. The schools do not have a special room as a learning facility for empowering dance as a learning style. Besides that, the learning media provided by the schools do not support the teachers in implementing dance as a learning style in the students' learning process. Limited teachers' competences are also a problem in implementing dance learning as a learning style, due to the lack of training provided for teachers in communicating that learning instruction can be delivered by empowering the potential of dance as a learning style. Another problem related to the students' conditions is that, in implementing dance learning as a learning style with many students, they will have difficulty mastering the learning. This is because, with many students, the teachers will need a long time to teach them.

Diagram 1 also shows that 23.1% of the teachers interviewed had implemented dance as a learning style. Some of the things that support teachers in implementing dance learning as a learning style include collaborating with parents and the school to support each other actively. The parents facilitate the needs of teachers in implementing dance as a learning style in the classroom. The students' parents provide the teachers with facilities by collaborating with parties outside of school that support the teachers' programs in implementing dance as a learning style. The parents help the teachers by providing learning facilities, bringing the dance

teachers from outside the school to help the teachers implement dance as a learning style. In addition, school facilities are supporting it, one of which is that the schools already have a special room for dance and equipment to support the learning process in dance as a learning style.

From diagram 1, the result of 7.7% of the teachers' interviews had been implemented, but still infrequently. This problem is caused by several things, including the teachers' lack of motivation to implement dance as a learning. In addition, the parents' supports in collaborating with teachers in synergy in the learning process also still lack, so the teachers have difficulty in conditioning the students in preparing for learning by applying dance as a learning style. Unsupportive students' conditions also cause the teachers to have trouble in implementing dance as a learning style.

The Results of Teachers' Perceptions of the Potential of Dance as a Teaching Style

Diagram 2: The Results of teachers' perceptions of the potential dance as a teaching style

From diagram 2, it can be explained that the results of interviews with the teachers show that teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a learning style respond to 86% that dance can help students know well (*knowing the good things*). Through dance as a learning style, the teachers perceive that the students will find it easier to capture a message in learning materials. With movements presented in the form of dance to convey an abstract message or instruction, so that the students will better understand the meaning of the learning material. The students will easily receive the messages if the messages are presented in a holistic form, especially for elementary school students.

The potential aspects of dance as a learning style make the students more interested (*desiring the good things*). The teachers' interviews showed that 81% of the teachers stated that dance as a learning style impacts the students' interest or desire in learning. This can be explained that by applying dance as a learning style, the students are more interested in learning the

material. This can happen because of the dance, the learning material will be more interesting. It contains aesthetic elements that can finally affect the students' social emotions.

In the aspect of the potential of dance as a learning style, it makes the students easier to imitate well (*exemplifying the good things*), the results of the teachers' interviews gave a response of 85% of the teachers perceived that dance as a learning instruction had an impact on students to imitate well easily. The results of the teachers' responses are based on the learning that the teachers have carried out. The teachers provide stimulus to students during learning with the concept of dance. At the end of the lesson, the students show an attitude of more easily imitating what the teachers have instructed, which provides evidence that dance as a learning style has a good influence on students' learning outcomes.

In the aspect of the potential of dance as a learning style, it helps the students to love appropriately. The teachers' interviews showed that 85% of the teachers responded that dance can help students love easily and properly (*loving the good things*). The teachers' perception is based on the results of the learning that has been done. The teachers deliver learning with dance as a learning instruction; then, the teachers record the results of the assessment of the learning outcome process. At the end of learning, it shows that the students love or like learning material more if it is presented by something interesting, including through dance movements.

In the aspect of the potential of dance as a learning style make easier the students to practice or do well (*acting the good*), the results of teacher interviews gave a response of 89% of teachers perceived that dance as a learning style has a very significant impact on the good practices which carried out by students. This can be explained by the fact that dance as a learning style greatly impacts the good practices carried out by students. This is the result of dance, which can be used as an engaging learning instruction because dance has elements like movement that encourage students to practice directly in learning.

Discussion

The Results of communicating dance in learning as a learning style

Communicating dance in learning as a learning style is one of the systematic efforts to overcome discrepancies based on the problems which was identified in this research. Based on the interviews, several aspects show that communicating dance in learning has been implemented by the teachers. The results of the interviews show that 23.1% of the teachers have implemented dance learning as a learning style, 7.7% have implemented it but still infrequently. But some have not implemented, the data shows that 69.2% of the teachers have not implemented dance learning as a learning style, this shows that potential of dance as a learning style still needs to be communicated more intensively to the teachers and education stakeholders so the potential of dance as a learning style can be maximized in learning.

To communicate the dance as a learning style, it requires some motivation and support, which are not only from the teachers but also from the school as well. In addition, the teachers also need to build the students' interest by creating learning motivations, especially through dance

as a learning style. The results of the teachers' interviews show that 81% of the teachers stated that dance as a learning style impacted students' interest or desire in learning. This needs to be strengthened by presenting new ideas in learning that are offered with dance as a learning style it. Furthermore, the teachers' perceptions show that 85% of the teachers responded that dance as a learning instruction had an impact on the students in imitating learning more easily, and dance can also have an effect on the students for liking learning easily. These results are good enough, so the teachers' strategies are needed to enable students to stay in conducive learning conditions. To make the students stay with conducive learning conditions, the teachers need to collaborate on dance not only with one subject but also to be elaborated with other subjects, to impact the students' knowledge (currently 86%). This expectation will ultimately also affect the students' practical activities in learning (currently 89%). Creating an active role and giving opportunities for students to develop creativity are ways of building an active role directly in the learning process.

These results are consistent with a previous study conducted by Zhang et al. (2021), who also researched the potential of dance as a learning style. Their findings showed that applying dance as a learning style and instructional tool could be integrated into language learning. Through dance learning, language acquisition can be supported, connecting with all nervous systems, ultimately impacting the children's kinesthetic intelligence. (Zhang et al., 2021) found that integrating dance with language learning positively influences children's learning abilities. But, research by Zhang et al. (2021) only focused on the linguistic aspect. This difference may be due to variations in learning styles and the backgrounds of research subjects. Combining dance and language learning as a learning style requires movements that incorporate aesthetics, transforming abstract concepts into tangible experiences, ultimately creating enjoyable learning (Elita et al., 2021).

The Impact of Communicating Dance in Learning as a Learning Style

The results of this research provide an overview of communicating dance as a learning instruction and teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a learning style. From the interviews, teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a learning style revealed the following responses: 86% of the teachers stated that dance could positively impact students' abilities to understand well (*knowing the good things*), 81% of the teachers indicated that dance as a learning style affects students' interest or desire for learning (*desiring the good thing*), 85% of the teachers perceived that dance as a learning instruction makes the students easier to imitate well (*exemplifying the good things*), 85% of the teachers responded that dance could positively influence the students to love properly (*loving the good things*), 89% of the teachers believed that dance as a learning style had a significant impact on the positive practices carried out by the students (*acting the good*)

The results of the research are consistent with the findings by Malarsih (2016) which showed that learning through dance as a learning instruction positively impacts the students activities, particularly in terms of appreciations and creativities (*acting the good things*) so that it can encourage the students to be motivated in learning, which in the end affect their interest in learning (*desiring the good things*). Additionally, Hanna (2008) emphasised the complexity

and importance of dance as nonverbal communication can provide depth to the teachers' explanations when they ask the students to create, perform, observe, critique, and analyse problems within learning. Furthermore, Singh and Devi (2021) found that dance helps the students realize their potentials for self-development, confidence, problem-solving, and creativity so that this process allows students to recognize the importance of communicating dance as a learning instruction and the potential of dance as a learning style, which ultimately impacts the desired learning outcomes for both the teachers and students.

Research Limitation

One of the limitations of this research is that not all the teachers are masters in dance competencies. Not every teacher feels confident communicating dance as a learning instruction and dance as a learning style. However, the potential of dance as a learning style is promising for improving the qualities of the students' learning, both in terms of learning outcomes and character development. With adequate opportunities and a commitment from the teachers to make efforts in communicating dance as a learning instruction and a learning style, it is hoped that the teachers can continue to develop the potential of dance in these aspects. Ultimately, this could enhance the students' learning facilities to produce a meaningful learning experience. Future classroom-based research in education, particularly in communicating dance as a learning instruction and dance as a learning style, is valuable for improving learning outcomes and developing the students' creativity. Further research should explore how and why dance can contribute to developing potential in character education.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research found that communicating dance as a learning instruction and dance as a learning style is still not optimal. Although some aspects are relatively well-developed, such as the results of interviews conducted with 26 elementary school teachers in Semarang City, many teachers have not developed learning by communicating dance as a learning style. The interview results reveal that 69.2% of the teachers have not implemented dance as a learning style, 23.1% have implemented it, and 7.7% have implemented it but infrequently. Then, the teachers' perceptions of the potential of dance as a learning style provide several responses; 86% of teachers agree that dance can help students to gain knowledge effectively (*knowing the good things*), 81% of the teachers state that dance as a learning style positively impacts the students' interest and motivation in learning (*desiring the good things*), 85% of the teachers perceive that dance as learning instruction helps the students easily imitate well (*examplifying the good things*), 85% of the teachers respond that dance help students easily love properly (*loving the good things*), 89% of the teachers percept that dance as a learning style significantly contributes to the good practices demonstrated by students (*acting the good things*).

Further research is recommended to develop more innovative and creative strategies for communicating dance as a learning instruction and dance as a learning style. An experimental study can evaluate the effectiveness of various active learning methods involving dance in the classroom as an instructional and learning style. On the other hand, further research must explore how constructive feedback and deeper reflection can be integrated when

communicating dance as instructional learning and as a learning style. Investigating the teachers' understanding of communicating dance as instructional learning and dance as a learning style is also essential to support the development of dance as instructional learning and dance as a learning style for better implementation.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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